

TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATIONS OF COMPOSITES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

An overview of the technology development and applications of composites in India is presented. Developments in various sectors such as Aerospace, Defence, general engineering, biomedical, sports and commercial products are briefly described covering a wide range of technologies from autoclave moulding and filament winding of aerospace components, to wet lay-up and moulding of low cost GRP products. The applications are widespread but consumption levels are low owing to a lack of user acceptance and other techno-economic reasons. A sound base for the growth of composites has been created and a significantly high growth rate is expected in near future.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been in use in India for last three decades. Indigenous production of unsaturated polyester resins started in 1962 and of glass fibres in 1965 laying the foundation for the growth of composites in the country. From the initial days of contact moulding of simple products such as helmets, tanks, boats etc., the composites technology has grown to encompass a wide spectrum of engineering and consumer products. Processes such as filament winding, injection moulding, resin transfer moulding, pultrusion, centrifugal casting, vacuum bag and autoclave moulding have been developed to make a range of sophisticated products including vital components of aircraft, spacecraft, missiles, satellites and load bearing structures. The range of materials used has also expanded to include not only fibre reinforced polymer composites of various kinds but also sandwich constructions, metal-matrix and ceramic-matrix composites. This has been achieved through a consistent effort in R&D at Universities and Research Laboratories coupled with product development in Government and private industries. Country's leading organisations such as Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO), Hindustan Aeronautics Limited (HAL), Defence R&D Organisation (DRDO), National Aerospace Laboratories (NAL), Aeronautical Development Agency (ADA) and private Industries as well as professional societies such as Indian Society for Advancement of Materials and Process Engineering (ISAMPE), All-India Reinforced Plastics Moulders Association (AIRPMA) and Aeronautical Society of India (AeSI) have identified Composites as one of the vital areas for the growth in the country. As a result, composites technology and industry are poised for significant growth in the near future.

This paper attempts to give an overview of status of composite technology and applications in the country and highlights some of the issues pertaining to growth of composites in India.

CATEGORIES OF USAGE OF COMPOSITES

The applications and usage of composites in India encompasses a wide variety of products and processes. These can be broadly put into three categories for the purpose of discussion in this paper. **High Performance Area** : This forms the high-tech end of the spectrum and comprises mainly of Aerospace sector with applications in aircraft, launch vehicles, satellites, missiles, etc. The volume of consumption in this category is low but the technology requirements are of highest order. **High Volume / Commercial Area** : This consists of a very large range of products in both engineering and consumer sector which are produced commercially. The demand on the technology level is not as high as in the high performance area. **Speciality Area** : This consists of special applications where technology level and volume may be high or low but special considerations dictate the product development. Examples are biomedical applications and MMC and CMC applications at the present stage. The following sections give a brief summary of developments in each of above areas.

HIGH PERFORMANCE AREA

This sector covers the application areas where highest level of technology in terms of design, advanced materials and process technologies is required. Presently, such applications in India are basically in Aerospace Sector. The developments in this area have been spurred by the needs of the major projects undertaken in the country during the last fifteen years. Some of them can be listed as

Satellite Launch Vehicles (ASLV, PSLV)	Satellites - (INSAT series)
Advanced Light Helicopter (ALH)	Light Combat Aircraft (LCA)
Wind turbines	Pilotless Target Aircraft (PTA)
Rotodome (ASWAC)	NAL Light Aircraft (NALLA)

Some significant components developed and made under these programs are listed in Table 1 in order to illustrate the technological advances in this sector.

Satellites and Launch Vehicles

The ISRO were the pioneers in utilising composite materials in India. Early applications related to the use of glass and aramid fibre reinforced polymer composites for shell-like structures such as rocket-motor casings, Fig. 1a, using filament winding processes. Over the years, the expertise in this area has been consolidated with the use of indigenous winding machines and raw materials. Composites using silica cloth reinforcements were also developed indigenously and used for high temperature areas in rockets. Antenna dishes (Fig.1b) provided the next area of use of composites. Use of carbon fibre composites in making solar cell panels for satellites is relatively new but large honeycomb panels with thin carbon face sheets have been fabricated and used on INSAT satellites.

Aircraft and Helicopters

The use of composites for aircraft started in India in 1971 when glass-fibre reinforced plastics were used for secondary and tertiary components. These included fairings and doors for helicopters and soon expanded to other fairings, doors, nose cones, electrical boxes etc. in other aircraft programmes. Later, in the eighties, technology for metallic honeycomb sandwich components was acquired in the Jaguar programme. Drop tanks using asbestos-phenolic

composites were also made in this programme. Around the same time, moulded GRP and aramid composite parts for aircraft interior were made in Dornier programme.

Table 1. Some Composite Components made in the High-performance Sector

Component Description	Program	Year	Materials	Process
Rocket motor casings (650 mm dia x 1500 mm long to larger than 1m dia and 1.5 m long)	SLV-3 ASLV PSLV	1980 on-wards	Kevlar-epoxy & Glass-epoxy	Filament winding
Pressure Bottles for control systems (800 cc and larger)	-do-	-do-	Glass-epoxy	Filament winding
Heat-shields	-do-	-do-	Silica-phenolic sandwich	Autoclave moulding
Divergent Nozzles for rockets	-do-	-do-	Silica-phenolic	Tape winding
C-Band and C/S Antenna Dishes (1 m dia to 2 m dia) solar panel (2m x2m) and struts yoke, etc.	APPLE & INSAT	1981 on-wards	HM-graphite-epoxy prepreg & Al honeycomb	Autoclave moulding
Collapsible astromast (~ 10 m)	INSAT	1990	Glass-epoxy	Pultrusion
Wing and fuselage for a 2-seater small aircraft	NALLA PTA	1993	Glass-epoxy	Wet lay-up
Helicopter Rotor blade ("Hingeless Rotor") cockpit, frames, tailboom, body	ALH	1992	C, Glass- Kevlar/ epoxy, & foam	Autoclave moulding
Rotodome (7300 mm dia)	ASWAC	1994	Glass-epoxy Al honeycomb	Vac bag moulding
Aeroplane Wing	PTA	1993	Glass-epoxy	Wet layup
Aircraft rudder and fin and wing spars	LCA	1994 1995	Al honeycomb Carbon-epoxy	Co-cured; autoclave.

Figure 1. (a) Kevlar-epoxy Rocket motor casing and (b) Carbon-epoxy C/S Antenna dish and the Solar panel of INSAT Satellite under vibration test.

However, the biggest boost to composite usage has been provided by the indigenous programmes. A small light all composite (GRP) experimental aircraft was developed and flown by NAL in 1990 which formed the basis later for the composite light aircraft prototype HANSA.

The helicopter programme ALH was initiated in early eighties and the LCA programme in late eighties. Both the programmes make extensive use of composites, see Figs. 2,3. About 60% of the surface area of ALH is composites. Components developed include a single-piece moulded structure of the entire cockpit using carbon and aramid composites as well as a main motor blade using the concept of "hingeless-rotors". Fabrication technology using composite tooling itself has been established for ALH components. The LCA has about 30 % of its airframe weight in carbon epoxy composites. This includes primary structures such as wing and fin. Even though the large wing-skins are presently fabricated outside the country for lack of large-scale autoclave, all other components are fabricated indigenously. A major technology development in this area is the co-cured constructions and fabrication of the entire fin, Fig. 4. Whereas ALH and LCA programmes use advanced composites with prepregs and autoclave moulding, other low-cost technologies with indigenous materials have been successfully used to make glass fibre composite components such as wing of NALLA and PTA and Rotodome for ASWAC. The Rotodome shown in Fig. 5 is a large structure made in two sections with vacuum bag moulding.

Figure 2. Use of composites in the Advanced Light Helicopter. The entire cockpit is made as a single piece moulding in carbon and aramid fibre composites.

Figure 3. Light Combat Aircraft presently under development. About 30% airframe weight is in carbon-epoxy composites. Radome is made of aramid-polyester composite..

Figure 4. Co-Cured Co-bonded torsion box of LCA fin with its tooling.

Figure 5. The 7300 mm dia Rotodome for ASWAC made in Glass fibre composites..

Design and Analysis capabilities

A significant feature of these Aerospace programmes was the effort of indigenous design. Extensive analysis capabilities were developed and established through these programmes. Large scale computational facilities were integral to such programmes. Computer Aided Design and Analysis codes were either developed or bought out and implemented. Currently, design and analysis capabilities exist in the country for advanced composite structures. Most of the advanced software for composites are now in the country. These include MSC-NASTRAN, ASKA, ELFINI, CATIA, NISA, ANSYS, etc. The LCA programme, for example, has used large-scale structural optimisation with aeroelastic tailoring to make best use of the special properties of composites. An indigenous software - "AUTOLAY"- has been developed and integrated with CAD to generate optimum ply sequences accounting for the technological constraints.

Sponsored R & D

An important aspect of these programmes has been the involvement of premier academic institutions and research laboratories in addressing the design and technological problems and coming-up with solutions. This has led to wide spread interest in composites in the country's major institutions. The funding for these research programmes was drawn from the project funds itself. This resulted in time-bound research programmes aimed at resolution of specific issues.

HIGH VOLUME / COMMERCIAL AREA

The commercial sector includes a large number of products and applications which have grown over a period of last thirty years. These products use established materials and fabrication routes and, except for some specific engineering applications, do not generally involve any large-scale design effort. A summary of important products in various areas is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Key to categories of products manufactured in high volume / commercial sector.

Category	Applications / Products
Agricultural	Bio-gas/Gobar-gas plants, fertiliser hoppers, hatchery equipment, pens, poultry feed, sericulture equipment silos, tubewell pipes, water channels.
Automotive / Transportation	Bus, car and truck bodies; carports, dashboards, helmets, panels, road tankers, sidecars, trailers.
Pollution control and General engineering	Chlorination & water treatment equipment, septic tanks, weirs safety equipment, fan blades for wind mills, cooling towers and exhaust systems, Cross arms, electro mechanical parts, insulators, ladders, lamp covers, switchgear components, transformer housings, Business-machine and computer housing; cabinets, machine guards.
Construction	Cabins, domes, doors, facades, gutters, modular housing, panels, roofs, sanitary ware, shelters, sky lights, water tanks, window frames.
Furniture	Beds, benches, chairs, domestic & beauty parlour equipment, modular furniture, reception/waiting room seating, sofa sets, tables.
Marine	Buoys, canoes, fishing equipment, fishing/power/sail boats, floats, etc.
Recreation	Amusement-park equipment, diving boards, sports equipment, swimming pools and liners, tennis, squash rackets and golf sets.
Defence	Bullet proof vests, armours, cabins, gun cases, boxes, portable bridges.

Almost all the products use glass fibre reinforcements with polyester or epoxy resins. A consumption pattern of the glass-fibres in India is shown in Fig.6 which gives the relative proportion of usage in various applications sectors. A few applications use epoxy and phenolic resins and nylon or jute fibres. Tennis and squash rackets and walking sticks made out of carbon fibres are the latest additions to the growing list of commercial products. On the engineering side, an indigenous small car using glass fibre body has been on road for several years now. For most of the products in commercial sector, labour-intensive wet lay-up methods are used for fabrication. However, some product specific technologies are also in use for products like tennis rackets, bullet-proof vests and large fan blades for wind-mills or cooling towers. Recently, there is growing awareness of utilising the technologies developed in the high-performance sector on commercial scale for engineering products and this has led to technology transfer arrangements in a few areas.

SPECIALITY AREA**Biomedical Applications**

A major area which need special developmental efforts is the area of biomedical applications. Significant products developed under this category include orthopaedic appliances such as Floor Reaction Orthosis (FRO) for poliomyelitis patients and callipers for paraplegics (shown in Fig. 7) and prosthetic appliances such as stump foot and stump socket for lower limb

amputees. Potential for development of other such devices using composites is vast in the country. However, the major issue appears to be to provide such devices at an affordable cost.

Figure 6 Glass fibre consumption pattern in various sectors.

Figure 7 Biomedical applications of composites -Callipers for paraplegics.

Metal-Matrix and Ceramic-Matrix Components

The developments in MMC and CMC's range from laboratory demonstrations and prototype products to full scale commercial production in some cases. Fabrication routes for products using aluminium alloy, copper or magnesium alloy matrix with carbon, alumina or silicon-carbide fibres as reinforcements are being explored. Nickel and cobalt matrix with tungsten and carbide coatings co-deposited by detonation, diamond jet coating and electron deposition have been developed for high temperature erosion and corrosion resistance of jet engine components. Metal ceramic and polymer fibre ceramic friction materials have been developed and production facilities have been established for aircraft brakes. Development of ceramic-matrix composites using pre-ceramic polymers and sol-gel routes is being explored by at least two study groups in the country.

Figure 8(a)

Metal Ceramic brake pads for variety of aircraft

Figure 8(b)

Surface engineered jet engine components - Co-Cr-Carbide composite coatings by electro deposition

RELATED DEVELOPMENTS

Raw Materials

E-Glass-fibre is produced in the country by three manufacturers: the total installed capacity is about 2000 tonnes per annum. Almost all relevant forms (yarns, tows, fabrics, chopped-strand mats, etc.) required for composites are available. High performance S-glass is not yet produced on large scale. Carbon fibre production is only on a pilot-plant level. Aramid fibre technology is demonstrated on laboratory scale and commercial production is expected to start soon. Most of the epoxy, polyester and phenolic resins and low temperature thermoplastics are produced indigenously. However, some high performance grades of epoxies are not commercially produced even though the know-how exists. Intermediates such as SMC's and BMC's are produced on small scale; but "prepregs" required in high-performance sector are still in laboratory stage. The current developmental efforts to produce high quality prepregs are likely to come to fruition in the next couple of years. Other lab-scale achievements include high-temperature thermoplastics such as PEEK and PPS and technology for producing silicon carbide whiskers from rice-husk. A unique feature of some R&D efforts is to develop technologies to use low-cost locally available reinforcements such as natural fibres (like jute, cotton, coir, etc.) to produce composite products.

Quality Control, NDT, Testing etc.

The advent of the composite materials has brought forth the need for new quality control measures including non-destructive and destructive tests. Although standardisation has progressed to some extent with respect to glass-fibres and some GRP components, considerable scope exists for development of standards for Quality Assurance. In the high-performance sector, techniques using ultrasonics and X-rays have been developed and even large-scale indigenous scanning machines have been built, but the use of QC techniques has not carried over to commercial engineering applications.

R & D and Technology Transfer in Composites

The burden of R & D in a developing economy rests mainly on the Governmental funding. Most of the R & D work in the country is carried out in Government Laboratories and academic institutions. The Aeronautical Research & Development Board (ARDB) and Department of Science & Technology (DST) are the major sources of funding. For specific problems related to specific programmes, funding from respective programmes has been made available. Currently almost all the major research laboratories and academic institutions in the country have research groups working in the area of composites. Almost all the R & D is driven by the needs of the high performance sector or for special applications. However, recently a significant effort is being directed towards transfer of technology from this sector to the commercial sector. A special "Mission Mode" programme has been identified by DST for this purpose.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A broad base for the growth of composites technology has been created in India over last three decades. A wide spectrum of products ranging from the high tech Aerospace sector to low-cost consumer products are being produced in the country. The volume of composite usage is quite small compared to that in the West; but, the growth rates are high. The Composite Industry business which stands today at US\$100 million is expected to reach US\$ 400-500 by the year 2010. As the user acceptance grows, the composite usage in India is poised for a big leap forward.

(The information and data in this article are drawn from presentations made by several study groups in various National Seminars and Conferences in India over last five years.)